

Prevalence of Cervical Cancer Screening and Awareness among Women in an Urban Community in Eastern India: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer is still a major public health concern, particularly in low- and middle-income nations where screening and preventative care are not widely available. Due to logistical and socioeconomic obstacles, urban slum regions bear a disproportionately high incidence of cervical cancer, which is the second most frequent malignancy among women in India. The study evaluated women's knowledge and prevalence of cervical cancer screening as well as to pinpoint major obstacles to screening.

Methods: A six-month cross-sectional study including 400 women between the ages of 21 and 65 was carried out. Systematic random sampling was used to choose the participants, and structured interviews using a pre-tested questionnaire were used to gather data. SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data, and chi-square tests and descriptive statistics were used to determine whether the variables were related.

Results: Of the 400 participants, 45% were aware of screening techniques and 55% had heard of cervical cancer. Merely 20% had never had a Pap smear performed. Lack of awareness (fifty percent), financial constraints (30%), and fear or worry (20%) were the biggest obstacles to screening. There was no significant correlation identified between awareness and marital status ($\chi^2 = 3.2$, $p = 0.2$), but there was a strong correlation between education level and awareness of screening procedures ($\chi^2 = 24.6$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The study found that women in the Kankarbagh slum had poor screening rates but a reasonable awareness of cervical cancer. Awareness of screening techniques was strongly correlated with education level, emphasising the need for focused educational programs.

Recommendations: To improve cervical cancer screening rates, comprehensive educational programs tailored to women in urban slums should be implemented. Addressing financial constraints and alleviating fear through community engagement and support services are also crucial.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Screening, Awareness, Urban Slums.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer (CC) is still a major public health concern, especially in low- and middle-income nations where screening and preventative care are not widely available. It is the fourth most frequent cancer in women worldwide, accounting for 311,000 deaths and an expected 570,000 new cases in 2018 [1]. The high death rate linked to cervical cancer is mostly caused by late-stage diagnosis, which may be avoided with routine screening and early detection.

It has been demonstrated that screening initiatives, such the Papanicolaou (Pap) smear and human papillomavirus (HPV) test, considerably lower the incidence and death rate of cervical cancer [2]. These screening techniques are still not widely

used in many poor nations, despite their effectiveness, because of a mix of logistical, cultural, and socioeconomic obstacles. India is home to around 25% of the world's cases of CC, making it the second most frequent malignancy among women worldwide [3]. Nonetheless, there is a startling lack of knowledge and use of cervical cancer screening services in many areas, especially among marginalised groups like those residing in urban slums.

Urban slums represent a unique challenge for public health initiatives due to their high population density, poor living conditions, and limited access to healthcare services. Women in these areas are often deprived of basic health education and

preventive services, including cervical cancer screening. Factors such as low literacy levels, financial constraints, cultural taboos, and lack of awareness further exacerbate the situation [4].

By understanding the current levels of awareness and screening practices, this research seeks to identify key barriers and facilitators to CC screening in this community. The findings will provide crucial insights for designing effective educational and healthcare interventions tailored to the needs of women in urban slums. Addressing these issues is vital for achieving equitable healthcare and reducing the cervical cancer burden in underserved populations.

This study aims to assess the prevalence of cervical cancer screening and awareness among women in an urban community in Eastern India.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out for 6 months at Kankarbagh slum area, Patna, Bihar, India.

Participants: A total of 400 women from the Kankarbagh slum area in Patna participated in this study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Women aged 21-65 years
- Residents of the Kankarbagh slum area for 6 Months from June 2023 to December 2023

Exclusion Criteria

- Women who had a hysterectomy
- Women with a known history of cervical cancer

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were selected using systematic random sampling. Interviewer bias was reduced through standardized training and procedures. Recall bias was addressed by using clearly defined questions and cross-verifying information with medical records where possible.

Data Collection: A pre-tested questionnaire was used to conduct structured interviews that yielded data. The questionnaire addressed history of CC screening, awareness of CC and screening techniques, and sociodemographic data.

Procedure: Data collectors were trained to ensure uniformity in data collection. Systematic random sampling was used to select participants. Structured interviews were conducted at the participants' homes or a community center, ensuring privacy and confidentiality. Collected data were entered into a database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. To compile the data, descriptive statistics were employed. The relationships between the categorical variables were evaluated using chi-square testing. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

The study included 400 women from the Kankarbagh slum area in Patna. The age distribution ranged from 21 to 65 years, with a mean age of 37.5 years (SD = 10.2). The majority of the participants were married (85%), while the remaining were single, widowed, or divorced. Educational levels varied, with 45% having no formal education, 30% having completed primary education, 20% secondary education, and 5% higher education.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
21-30	100	25.0
31-40	120	30.0
41-50	110	27.5
51-65	70	17.5
Marital Status		
Married	340	85.0
Single	30	7.5
Widowed	20	5.0
Divorced	10	2.5
Education Level		
No formal education	180	45.0
Primary education	120	30.0
Secondary education	80	20.0
Higher education	20	5.0

Out of the 400 participants, 220 (55%) had heard about CC, and 180 (45%) were aware of CC screening methods.

Table 2: Awareness of Cervical Cancer and Screening

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Heard about CC	220	55.0
Aware of screening methods	180	45.0

Among the participants, only 80 (20%) had ever undergone a Pap smear test. The reasons cited for not undergoing screening included lack of awareness (50%), fear or anxiety (20%), and financial constraints (30%).

Table 3: Screening Practices

Screening Practices	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Ever undergone Pap smear test	80	20.0
Reasons for not undergoing screening		
Lack of awareness	160	50.0
Fear or anxiety	64	20.0
Financial constraints	96	30.0

The relationship between demographic characteristics and awareness of CC screening was investigated using a chi-square test. The knowledge of screening techniques and education level were

significantly correlated, according to the results ($\chi^2 = 24.6$, $p < 0.001$). Nevertheless, there was no discernible correlation between awareness and married status ($\chi^2 = 3.2$, $p = 0.2$).

Table 4: Association Between Demographic Factors and Screening Awareness

Variable	Awareness	Non-awareness	χ^2	p-value
Education Level				
No formal education	50	130	24.6	<0.001
Primary education	60	60		
Secondary education	50	30		
Higher education	20	0		
Marital Status				
Married	160	180	3.2	0.2
Single	10	20		
Widowed	5	15		
Divorced	5	5		

Discussion

Among the 400 participants, aged 21 to 65, a significant portion lacked formal education, and 30% the majority were married. Awareness of cervical cancer was relatively moderate, with 55% of women having heard about the disease, and 45% being aware of screening methods. However, only a small fraction (20%) had ever undergone a Pap smear test, indicating a significant gap between awareness and actual screening practices.

The primary barriers to screening identified were a lack of awareness, accounting for 50% of the responses, followed by financial constraints (30%) and fear or anxiety (20%). These findings suggest that even among women who are aware of CC and its screening methods, various socio-economic and psychological barriers impede their ability to undergo regular screening.

A statistical analysis showed a substantial correlation between knowledge of cervical cancer screening techniques and educational attainment. Higher educated women were more likely to be familiar with screening techniques, suggesting that educational initiatives may be essential to raising awareness and encouraging screening habits. However, there was no discernible correlation

between awareness and marital status, indicating that educational programs had to take into account all marital statuses.

The study's overall findings highlight the urgent need for financial and educational initiatives to improve women living in urban slums' knowledge of and use of CC screening. The noteworthy correlation between awareness and education underscores the possible influence of focused educational initiatives. By removing the obstacles that have been found, women's health outcomes in these communities may be improved in the long run through higher screening rates, earlier detection, and better management of cervical cancer.

A study on the prevalence of CC screening and women's understanding of the disease was carried out in a low-income urban population in South India. Just 7.1% of the 1033 women surveyed had had a cervical cancer screening, and 14.3% had had a pelvic check at least once in their lives. There was a general lack of information regarding cervical cancer, with 84.6% having low knowledge, 10.3% having moderate knowledge, and only 5.1% having strong knowledge. Younger ladies knew more about the illness [5].

A study conducted among 1500 women in Haryana, India's rural and urban areas, evaluated their knowledge about the HPV vaccine and cervical cancer. According to the study, 45% of women in cities and 55% of women in rural areas knew very little about cervical cancer. In both categories, women's knowledge of the HPV vaccine was extremely low: 95% of rural women and 75% of urban women did not know about it. The study made clear how important it is to implement educational initiatives to raise awareness and encourage early detection [6].

In another study, 1140 indigenous women in coastal Karnataka were assessed for their knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding cervical cancer screening. Just 2.3% knew that cervical cancer may be identified early, despite the fact that 82.9% of people had heard of it. Before the trial, none had had a cervical cancer screening. The knowledge scores showed a substantial correlation with socioeconomic status, age, marital status, education level, and tribal community [7].

219 women participated in an urban Pondicherry study to determine their awareness of and obstacles to cervical cancer screening. Of those surveyed, around one-third were aware of cervical cancer and 32 percent were eager to get screened. Fear and the idea that screening wasn't necessary in the absence of symptoms were major obstacles. Knowledge of risk factors, occupation, and family history of cancer were found to be important predictors of desire to undergo screening [8].

In a study, women visiting an Uttar Pradesh rural healthcare centre were asked about their knowledge of and participation in cervical cancer screening. While most participants were aware that CC was a form of cancer, few were aware of its signs, risk factors, or screening techniques. Numerous sexual encounters and illiteracy were important indicators of low awareness [9].

Research examined community healthcare workers in Varanasi's knowledge, attitudes, and screening procedures for cervical cancer. Less than 10% of employees had undergone screening, despite having high knowledge and favourable attitudes. The study underscored the necessity of educational initiatives aimed at closing the knowledge gap with practical application [10].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that expert tibial nail fixation is an effective and reliable method for managing distal tibia fractures. The procedure is associated with good functional outcomes, a low complication rate, and satisfactory healing times. These findings support the continued use of expert tibial nail fixation as a standard treatment option

for distal tibia fractures, highlighting its benefits in promoting functional recovery and minimizing complications.

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